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ABSTRACT E-BOOK

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FP06-3

Temporary dry eye symptoms following ptosis correction and blepharoplasty: a comparative analysis

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Purpose: To investigate the impact of levator muscle resection for ptosis correction, performed with and without upper blepharoplasty, on dry eye symptoms, and to assess the recovery trajectory of these symptoms over time.

Method: A total of 92 patients with unilateral ptosis were included in this prospective study and divided into three groups based on surgical intervention: Group A underwent ptosis correction alone, Group B underwent combined ptosis correction and upper blepharoplasty, and Group C underwent blepharoplasty alone. Dry eye parameters were evaluated preoperatively and postoperatively at 1, 3, and 6 months. The assessments included Tear Break-Up Time (TBUT), Schirmer test, corneal and conjunctival staining, and the Ocular Surface Disease Index (OSDI) questionnaire. Statistical analysis was performed to compare changes in dry eye symptoms across the groups over time.

Results: Postoperative dry eye symptoms showed a transient increase in Groups A and B, with the most significant changes noted in Group B. At the 1-month follow-up, patients in Group B exhibited a substantial reduction in TBUT, increased corneal and conjunctival staining, and higher OSDI scores compared to baseline, indicating greater ocular surface disruption. Symptoms in Group A were less severe but followed a similar pattern, while Group C demonstrated minimal changes in dry eye parameters.

By the 3-month follow-up, symptoms began to improve in all groups, and by the 6-month follow-up, parameters across all groups had nearly returned to baseline levels.

Conclusion: Combined ptosis correction and blepharoplasty are associated with a more pronounced and prolonged temporary increase in dry eye symptoms compared to ptosis correction or blepharoplasty alone.

However, the reversibility of these symptoms by 6 months postoperatively highlights the safety and efficacy of these surgical procedures when paired with appropriate patient monitoring and management.

FP06-4

War-related facial trauma in Ukraine: oculoplastic implications and the utility of Patient Specific Implants (PSI)

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Purpose: Eye trauma is estimated to account for 20% of all injuries in modern warfare. Due to widespread bombing and shelling in Ukraine, there are many patients with extensive facial injuries, including loss of eyes, eyelid injuries and orbital fractures.

This is an overview of a recent mission to Ukraine by a multi-specialty surgical team (incl. oculoplastics), arranged under the auspices of a charitable foundation.

Method: This is an observational case series, demonstrating facial injuries as a result of explosions with shock-wave and shrapnel trauma in a war-zone and utilizing Patient Specific Implants (PSI) for orbital reconstruction. A detailed documentation of all orbital cases was kept on file, including photographs and imaging. In addition, the design and configuration of PSI's was stored for each patient. A compilation of such cases will be used to illustrate each orbital trauma category unique to war.

Results: Eight cases of upper/midface trauma will be presented to illustrate the different war injuries. Most relevant surgical techniques and the implantation of PSI's will be covered. With respect to the orbital region, the most common deformities included traumatic telecanthus, hypovolemic/contracted anophthalmic sockets and traumatic eyelid malpositions. In addition, lagophthalmos with severe exposure was commonly found in traumatic VII nerve palsies.

Conclusion: This presentation will demonstrate the type and extent of injuries to the orbital area from shock-wave and shrapnel trauma, specific to war weapons of destruction. There is a distinct and unique pattern of damage, which is different from injuries seen in the general peacetime population. Patient Specific Implants play an important role in the reconstruction of such complex facial skeleton fractures.

FP06-5

A quantitative assessment of thyroid eye disease activity using magnetic resonance imaging: a novel method

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Purpose: The aim of this study was to determine whether quantitative measurements of extra-ocular muscles and structures on magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) correlate with disease activity in thyroid eye disease (TED).

Method: A retrospective review of 162 patients with TED, between June 2014 and June 2024, who underwent MR Orbits was conducted. The patients were separated into active (n=73) and inactive (n=89) group according to the disease status on MRI. T1-weighted imaging, T2-weighted imaging and STIR on MRI sequences were used to measure exophthalmos value, extra-ocular muscle diameters, orbital fat thickness and optic nerve diameters.

Independent T-test was carried out to determine statistical significance ($p < 0.005$) in structural measurements between active and inactive groups. Area under the receiver operating characteristic curve (AUC) analysis was used to determine diagnostic accuracy of structural measurements in predicting disease progression.

Results: Inferior Rectus (IR) and Medial Rectus (MR) muscle were significantly larger in patients with active TED ($p=0.002$ and $p=0.005$ respectively). Total EOM was also significantly larger in active TED ($p<0.001$).

Total EOM/Exophthalmos and Inferior Rectus/Total EOM ratios showed higher values in the active TED ($p=0.000$). ROC analysis showed that the cut-off point of Total EOM/Exophthalmos ratio was 0.647, with a sensitivity of 90.4% and specificity of 88.8%, whilst the Inferior Rectus/Total EOM ratio had a cut-off point of 0.362, with a sensitivity of 90.4% and a specificity of 87.6%.

Conclusion: This study is the first of its kind and we have proven that radiological parameters can be used to determine the progression of disease activity in TED.

Results: The case involved a 13-year-old child, I.F., initially treated for granulomatous uveitis of the right eye, complicated by neovascular glaucoma. The patient was placed on immunosuppressants, without improvement. The neovascular glaucoma was treated with panretinal photocoagulation combined with intravitreal anti-VEGF injections, along with oral and local hypotensive treatment. The patient developed exophthalmos in the right eye. Examination revealed negative light perception in the right eye, elevated intraocular pressure, and grade III exophthalmos, along with the appearance of a subconjunctival tumor infiltrate. The anterior segment examination showed corneal dystrophy with pupillary occlusion and no visible fundus. The left eye examination was normal, with 10/10 visual acuity. Ocular ultrasound of the right eye revealed a heterogeneous vitreous and partial temporal retinal detachment. A cranio-orbital CT scan revealed a tumoral process depending on the superior-external wall of the anterior and posterior segments. A tumor biopsy confirmed the diagnosis of ciliary body medulloepithelioma. Extension work-up was negative. The treatment involved exenteration combined with chemotherapy.

Conclusion: Ciliary body medulloepithelioma is a rare congenital intraocular tumor. Typically presenting in early childhood with leukocoria or an orbital mass. Ultrasound shows a hyperechoic mass. Histological study and immunohistochemistry are essential for confirming the diagnosis and classifying the tumor as either non-teratoid or teratoid, benign or malignant. Enucleation remains the treatment of choice. Progression is usually very slow.

RF04-5

Management dilemmas in bilateral choroidal melanoma: a case report

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Purpose: Managing bilateral choroidal melanoma presents significant challenges, particularly in monocular patients, where the balance between tumor control and vision preservation is critical.

Case report: This report describes a 44-year-old patient who underwent enucleation of the left eye in 2021 due to advanced choroidal melanoma. Subsequently, a small juxtapapillary melanoma was detected in the right eye during regular monitoring. With a baseline visual acuity of 1.0 in the right eye, transpupillary thermotherapy (TTT) was performed in September 2022 to control tumor progression and preserve vision. Despite initial tumor management goals, TTT resulted in severe complications, including vitreous hemorrhage and progressive visual loss. By February 2023, visual acuity had declined to 1/60, necessitating a combined vitrectomy and cataract surgery.

Postoperative assessments revealed juxtapapillary scarring, pigmentary changes, and partial retinal detachment. Ultrasonographic imaging confirmed the tumor remains under control; however, the patient has experienced significant visual loss and dissatisfaction with the outcome, underscoring the impact on quality of life.

Results: This case highlights the complex challenges of managing juxtapapillary melanomas in monocular patients. While TTT remains a viable option for tumor control, its potential for sight-threatening complications underscores the necessity of thorough risk assessment and patient counseling. Alternative therapies, such as plaque brachytherapy or systemic treatments, may provide more balanced outcomes in certain cases.

Conclusion: Effective management of bilateral choroidal melanoma requires a multidisciplinary approach that prioritizes both vision preservation and tumor control. This case highlights the critical need for individualized treatment strategies, careful procedural planning, and consideration of emerging therapeutic options to mitigate complications and optimize patient outcomes.

RF04-6

Ocular surface squamous neoplasia in a healthy young patient

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Introduction: Ocular surface squamous neoplasia (OSSN) is relatively rare, with an incidence of 0.13-1.9 per 100 000. It encompasses a range of dysplastic lesions involving the squamous epithelium of the conjunctiva or cornea. It is more common in males between the ages of 50 and 75 years. Fair skin, a past history of skin cancer and immunosuppression increase the risk.

Methods: Clinical case review.

Case Report: We report a case of a 31-year-old melanodermic male, evacuated from São Tome island, with concerns about an enlarging mass on his left eye, for 1 year. Visual acuity was hand motion. A 12 x 8 mm corneal mass extending from 6:00 to 12:00 hours from the nasal limbus to the level of the temporal iris collarette was observed at the slit-lamp. The lesion was fixed, elevated, with an irregular papillomatous surface and vascular core.

Fundus examination was impossible due to visual axis obstruction. Ocular ultrasound showed an intact posterior segment. Ultrasound biomicroscopy was negative for anterior chamber invasion. Anterior segment OCT revealed thickened, hyperreflective epithelial tissue, with cystic spaces. HIV testing was negative.

The patient underwent an excisional biopsy with cryotherapy, absolute alcohol and amniotic membrane graft. Histopathologic analysis demonstrated conjunctival intraepithelial neoplasia, which coincided with the specimen margin. Mitomycin C was started as an adjuvant treatment (3 cycles of 0.04% topical mitomycin for a week, with 2 weeks intervals).

At the 3rd month post-operative visit, visual acuity was 20/40, there was only mild nasal conjunctival injection and the cornea was transparent, remaining a subtle nasal leucoma, with no recurrences.

Conclusion: We report an exuberant OSSN in a young patient, without any traditional risk factors. Lesion size at diagnosis could be explained by the delay in diagnosis in an evacuated patient. Young patients with OSSN should have HIV testing.

EP-EDU-12

Fasting and eye health: a clearer vision through faith and science

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Fasting has been the mainstay of spirituality for centuries, bringing discipline and mindfulness to people and connecting them to the divine. In recent years, science has taken a special interest in the physiological effects of fasting, including on ocular health.

Purpose: This study aims to assess the impact of short-term dietary restrictions due to religious fasting on eye health, which will offer valuable guidance for developing clinical guidelines on maintaining optimal eye health during fasting.

Methods: A comprehensive literature search was performed for studies and evidence related to the effects of fasting on ocular health using NCBI, AAO, AJO, and PubMed databases.

Results: Our findings emphasize the intricate relationship between fasting and ocular well-being. Ramadan fasting may alter IOP, while Orthodox fasting reduces oxidative stress and has anti-inflammatory benefits. Exclusion of animal proteins can affect eye health differently based on personal dietary habits. Although plant proteins provide essential amino acids, a diverse diet is crucial for the absorption of nutrients.

Also, red meat consumption, providing some detrimental substances, may alter the functionality of retinal pigment epithelium (RPE) cells and consequently lead to age-related macular degeneration (AMD). Nutrients from plants, such as Vitamins A, lutein, zeaxanthin, and Omega-3 fatty acids, help with eye health by improving hydration and reducing inflammation.

Conclusion: Religious fasting may affect ocular health in various aspects depending on fasting duration, type of dietary restriction, and hydration. While both animal and plant proteins are important for eye health, a well-planned, balanced diet devoid of animal protein can help individuals achieve their eye-health-related targets by obtaining food from various plant sources to adequately meet their essential nutrient requirements. It's advisable to keep track of nutrient levels being controlled and to supplement if needed.

ELECTRONIC POSTER PRESENTATIONS

Electronic Posters: External Eye

EP-EXE-01

Orbital cellulitis induced by *Chinavia hiliaris*: first documented case in a 19-year-old male

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Purpose: To present the first documented case of orbital cellulitis caused by *Chinavia hiliaris* (stink bug) in a 19-year-old male without prior trauma or systemic illness, highlighting the diagnostic and therapeutic challenges of this rare etiology.

Case report: A 19-year-old male presented with painful swelling of the right upper and lower eyelids following exposure to *Chinavia hiliaris*. He reported that the insect had entered his eye the day prior. Examination revealed proptosis, conjunctival chemosis, mixed conjunctival hyperemia, and restricted ocular motility with diplopia in certain gaze directions. Visual acuity was 0.7 in the right eye and 1.0 in the left, with intraocular pressure of 11/13 mmHg. MDCT imaging showed proptosis of the right globe, diffuse thickening of periorbital soft tissues, and thickening of the optic nerve, consistent with orbital cellulitis.

Funduscopy could not be performed due to eyelid edema. The patient was promptly admitted and treated with intravenous antibiotics (Longaceph 2g and Amikacin 500mg twice daily) and corticosteroids (Lemod-Solu 120mg, tapered daily).

Discussion: Orbital cellulitis is typically associated with sinus infections or trauma. This case is unique in identifying *Chinavia hiliaris* as the causative agent, with no preceding injury or systemic illness. Stink bugs are not commonly associated with human infections, but their potential to introduce pathogens via exposure warrants consideration in differential diagnoses of orbital cellulitis.

Early imaging and aggressive management with intravenous antibiotics and corticosteroids were critical in addressing inflammation and preventing complications.

Conclusion: This first reported case of *Chinavia hiliaris*-induced orbital cellulitis highlights the need for awareness of rare environmental exposures in the etiology of orbital infections. Prompt diagnosis and early intervention are essential to prevent vision-threatening complications in such rare and atypical presentations.

EP-ONC-09

Stereotactic radiosurgery irradiation planning scheme of uveal melanoma with and without artificial intelligence

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Purpose: Radiosurgery at a linear accelerator is one of the possibilities to treat uveal melanoma. Stereotactic radiosurgery is provided with the use LINAC linear accelerator TRUEBeam STX dedicated to stereotactic irradiation. At the Department of Radiation oncology at the Oncological Institute of St. Elizabeth (OUSA) there are two completely identical LINAC -TRUEBeams. For uveal melanomas we are using 6 MV photons.

Method: Since November 2024 we introduced the use of artificial intelligence (AI). The goal is to reduce time necessary for contouring of critical structures (e.g. optical nerves, chiasma, brain stem, anterior segment) and eliminate interobserver variability in contouring these structures.

By one-day session irradiation we are using rigid-frame-based fixation, immobilization of the affected eye is achieved by mechanical fixation of direct extraocular muscles to the stereotactic frame. After image fusion of CT and MRI, critical structures (e.g. optic nerves, chiasma, brainstem, cochlea and lens) were contoured by AI or radiation oncologist. The applied radiation dose for melanomas is 35.0 Gy to the margin.

Results: The final individual plane created by AI in comparison with manual contouring could save time but it is still necessary to make corrections by the treating physician.

Conclusion: The introduction of AI into treatment planning is a step towards standardization of the contouring of critical structures while saving time. Nevertheless, the contours must still be approved by team doctors and correlate with anatomical atlases and guidelines.

The critical steps—such as importing images into treatment planning systems, and co-registering diagnostic images to treatment planning studies which are used for dosimetry calculation, target volume delineation, treatment plan development, evaluation of isodose distributions, treatment delivery, require significant manual effort and therefore are subject to substantial inter-physician cooperation.

EP-ONC-10

Surgical difficulties in the management of squamous cell carcinoma of the eyelid with xeroderma pigmentosum: about a case

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Xeroderma pigmentosum is a rare genetic disease, transmitted in an autosomal recessive fashion. It is characterized clinically by extreme photosensitivity of the skin, pigmentary abnormalities of the skin exposed to the sun with an increased risk of skin cancer development and damage ophthalmic and neurological.

We describe a case of squamous cell carcinoma of the eyelid in a young male patient, aged 25, with a history of xeroderma pigmentosum. The patient underwent oncological tumor resection with eyelid reconstruction.

Ophthalmologic examination at the level of the right eye found on inspection red-eye with a lesion occupying the outer 1/3 of the free edge of the lower right eyelid and the anterior segment biomicroscopy reveals conjunctival hyperemia, diffuse and moderate with the presence of an ulcerative budding mass, measuring 1cm, occupying the outer 1/3 of the free edge of the lower right eyelid.

The patient underwent oncological excisional surgery, the excisional piece was sent for anatomopathological examination to assess the excision margins. Eyelid reconstruction was performed using a Mustardé rotational myocutaneous flap.

Keywords: Xeroderma pigmentosum; squamous cell carcinoma; eyelid reconstruction; eyelid tumor

EP-ONC-11

Sclerochoroidal calcifications: a diagnostic challenge in subretinal lesions

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Purpose: Choroidal osteoma is a rare, benign ossifying tumor that can closely mimic other subretinal pathologies, posing significant diagnostic challenges.

This case report highlights a patient with a subretinal lesion initially presumed to be a choroidal osteoma, which was subsequently identified as sclerochoroidal calcifications, a rare condition that is often idiopathic or associated with metabolic imbalances involving calcium and phosphorus.

Case report: A 62-year-old male presented with a subretinal lesion located on the superior periphery of the left fundus. Ultrasonography revealed a plaque-like lesion measuring 9.96 x 8.07 mm in base and 1.05-1.54 mm in thickness, characterized by high reflectivity and acoustic shadowing, initially raising suspicion for a choroidal osteoma.

Fundus examination identified a yellowish, placoid subretinal lesion with irregular borders and intact retinal vessels traversing its surface. Fluorescein angiography demonstrated arterial phase hypofluorescence with subsequent heterogeneous staining of the lesion, persisting without leakage in later phases. These findings were more consistent with sclerochoroidal calcifications rather than a choroidal osteoma.

Results: Sclerochoroidal calcifications are rare subretinal changes that may mimic other conditions such as choroidal osteoma or metastatic lesions. Imaging plays a pivotal role in differentiation, with ultrasonography confirming calcifications and fluorescein angiography excluding vascular lesions. Unlike osteomas, sclerochoroidal calcifications are typically placoid, yellowish, and may be bilateral, often associated with metabolic abnormalities.

Conclusion: This case underscores the diagnostic complexity of subretinal lesions and the importance of multimodal imaging in differentiating sclerochoroidal calcifications from other pathologies. Accurate diagnosis ensures appropriate management and better patient outcomes.

EP-ONC-12

MALT lymphoma of the uvea with massive scleral and optic nerve infiltration: a case report

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Purpose: To present a rare case of extranodal marginal zone lymphoma (MALT lymphoma) of the uvea with extensive transscleral and optic nerve infiltration, highlighting the diagnostic, therapeutic, and surveillance challenges of managing an indolent lymphoma with aggressive local manifestations.

Case report: A 74-year-old male with a history of diabetes mellitus, hypertension, and prior ophthalmic surgeries, including glaucoma surgery (2017) and cataract extraction, presented with progressive pain, periorbital hemorrhage, and complete vision loss in the left eye.

Following a diagnosis of endophthalmitis, enucleation of the left globe was performed on September 12, 2024. Macroscopic examination revealed diffuse subretinal lesions extending across the nasal and temporal halves of the globe, with the largest lesion measuring 25 mm in base and 4 mm in prominence. Tumorous infiltration was observed through the sclera into the optic nerve and periorbital tissues.

Results: Histopathological analysis revealed a diffuse lymphoid infiltrate predominantly composed of small monocitoid lymphoid cells, with occasional lymphoblasts and immunoblasts. Immunohistochemical evaluation confirmed a B-cell phenotype (CD20+, CD79a+, Bcl-2+, MUM-1+) with low proliferative activity (Ki-67 < 5%), consistent with extranodal MALT lymphoma. Systemic evaluation via MSCT and MR imaging showed no evidence of dissemination or residual disease.

Laboratory tests, including serologies, were normal. Considering the lymphoma's indolent nature, no systemic therapy was initiated, and the patient was placed under regular surveillance.

Conclusion: This case highlights the rare presentation of MALT lymphoma of the uvea with transscleral and optic nerve invasion. It underscores the importance of histopathological and immunohistochemical analysis for accurate diagnosis and effective management. Regular follow-up is essential to monitor for recurrence or progression.

EP-ONC-13

Reactive retinal astrocytic gliosis with vasoproliferative features: a case report

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Purpose: To present a rare case of nodular reactive retinal astrocytic gliosis with vasoproliferative features, emphasizing its clinical presentation, imaging characteristics, and histopathological findings to support accurate diagnosis and effective management.

Case report: A 64-year-old female presented with progressive vision loss and elevated intraocular pressure in the right eye, unresponsive to medical therapy. She had undergone cataract surgery several years earlier at another institution. Visual acuity was limited to light perception.

Examination revealed a dense anterior chamber with medium-reflectivity content, circumferential iris displacement, and a subluxated intraocular lens (IOL) with fibrous opacities. Corneal opacity obscured deeper structures, but ultrasonography revealed vitreous hemorrhage, preretinal fibrous bands, and a temporal retinal lesion measuring 9.55 mm in base and 2.79 mm in prominence, with retinoschisis.

Due to the severity of the condition, enucleation of the right eye was performed. Histopathology confirmed nodular reactive retinal astrocytic gliosis with vasoproliferative features, explaining the progressive symptoms.

Results: Examination revealed significant degenerative changes, including cholesterol deposits and chronic inflammation, accompanied by extensive gliotic proliferation (GFAP+++), focal p53 expression, low proliferative activity (Ki-67 < 3%), and advanced retinal and optic nerve atrophy, highlighting the chronic and reactive nature of the condition.

Conclusion: This case highlights the rare presentation of reactive retinal astrocytic gliosis with vasoproliferative features, emphasizing its potential to mimic intraocular tumors. Imaging and histopathological analysis are essential for diagnosis, particularly in cases with corneal opacity and prior ocular surgeries. Early differentiation from neoplastic conditions is critical for effective management.

EP-ONC-14

Rare occurrence of choroidal melanoma in an atrophic bulbus: a case report

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Purpose: Choroidal melanoma is the most common primary intraocular malignancy in adults, but its occurrence in an atrophic bulbus is exceedingly rare, presenting a unique diagnostic and therapeutic challenge.

Case report: This case report presents a 71-year-old female patient with a history of severe ocular atrophy, whose enucleated globe revealed a choroidal melanoma, staged as *pT1a G1 (I)*.

The atrophic globe measured 20x18x19 mm with a visible, sectioned optic nerve at 13-16 mm from the scleral margin.

Macroscopically, the globe exhibited features of advanced atrophy and pigmentation in the posterior segment.

Microscopically, the tumor demonstrated diffuse immunoreactivity for Melan-A, HMB-45, SOX10, and S100, consistent with melanoma. The proliferation marker Ki-67 was low (<3%), indicating a slow-growing lesion.